

EFFECT OF HUMAN RESOURCES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF COUNTY GOVERNMENT OF GARISSA, KENYA

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Abstract: Since the inception of County government in 2010, the counties have been experiencing a number of challenges in the enhancing their performance. Accordingly, in spite of the various measures being undertaken to ensure the units of devolution work to achieve their objectives, there are few studies on the performance management on counties as this is a new phenomenon in Kenya on organizational performance. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the effect of human resources on the performance of County Government of Garissa, Kenya. The research design employed by the research study was descriptive design. This design is recommended as it helped in the provision of accurate information. The target population of the study was Garissa County Government. The respondents on the other hand were made up of senior management officials within the county of Garissa. The sampling design for the study was stratified sampling method that enabled the target population be grouped in form of strata for equitable representation. The study sample size was 101 respondents. The data collection instrument for the study was semi-structured questionnaires that was useful in obtaining primary data. 10% of the study sample size was part of the pilot group from which they were not included in the final research. Content validity was used in testing the validity of the questions within the questionnaire whereas reliability was obtained following a test on Cronbach Alpha. Quantitative data achieved by the survey was presented in the form of mean averages. Besides, statistical analysis software version 25 was also incorporated into the data analysis. Analysis of the qualitative data was done through content analysis. The findings from the study indicated that human resources greatly affect Garissa County Government's performance. With the positive correlation between human resources and the performance of Garissa County, it was also concluded that human resources are an important part of the County's overall strategic strategy. The study recommended that the county directors need to ensure the right employees who can work towards achieving similar goals within the county government of Garissa to encourage a greater team spirit are hired.

Keywords: Human Resources, Performance, Strategic Resources.

1. INTRODUCTION

Strategic management involves coordination, planning, decision-making decisions, planning, coordinating, and action taking by the organization's top management to achieve the desired goals and objectives. The organizations must take action towards implementing these strategies. This may, however, require the top management to effectively allocate all the needed resources and channel he organization to achieve the clear picture of the intended strategies (Dess et al., 2005). Participation of the top management is necessary since it involves critical decision machining on a long-term basis which needs substantial resources.

Leveraging of resources is helpful in the creation of competitive advantage that further helps in the conferment of performance opportunities. As a result of heterogeneity of resources, different organizations may have adequate strategic resources compared to the rest (Collis & Montgomery (2015). Organizational resources are essential to a firm's performance,

claim Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner, and Schaufeli (2015). They help employees become more skilled, lessen work-related stress, and advance their personal development. Therefore, strategic resources illustrate performance based on the economic value created by an organization.

Chatterjee and Wernerfelt (2016) observe that resources have frequently been characterized as organizational contingencies. The appropriate strategy is essential for effective alignment to the environmental contingencies' resources. A higher performance level can easily be achieved upon achieving this fit. Similarly, Black and Boal (2016) observe that Organizations that perform well are characterized by effectively linking daily organizational operations and available strategic resources. It is crucial to match strategic resources with organizational management actions as a result.

It can be predicted by the firm's resource-based approach that several resources controlled and owned by organizations can significantly contribute to increased performance (Geringer & Hebert, 2014). Pearce and Robinson (2016) observed that the resource-based approach indicates that to achieve more excellent performance at the organizational level, the strategic management drivers to more excellent performance are often resource capability and characteristics. This will further help in effectively implementing the desired strategies hence improving organizational efficiency.

Zgarrick (2015) demonstrates that human resources in Pakistan are essential to the pharmacy field in pharmaceutical industry. The pharmacist technician has good perceiving skills and can deliver higher performance. In addition, Gibson (2018) demonstrates that strategic resources are the central hub of the industries in achieving performance through financial, human, and physical resources. These resources the organization in carrying out the necessary activities required in achieving industrial objectives and targets. Therefore, it can be argued that proper practices on resources form the bases of the competitive background of the Pakistan pharmaceutical firms. They are a decisive and important aspect of the performance of organizations.

According to Oladipo and Abdulkadir (2018), consistent personnel training and staff development, appraisal systems for performance, equity-based compensation system, robust employee participation, and effective career planning system are human resource actions that have had an important on the success of organizations in the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria. The two authors further highlighted that those manufacturing firms in Nigeria need to be keen on these practices to improve performance across the industry. Recognition of Human Resource Management (HRM) practices as essential aspects of achieving a competitive advantage is critical in elevating organizational performance.

Gakenia, Muathe, and Bula (2015) observe that intangible resources, strategic positioning and skills possessed by the firm contribute to a significant performance of mobile phone companies in Kenya. They aid these companies in coming up wit and adopting several ways which can be useful in the improvement of a firm's effectiveness. Similarly, Mudogo (2019) observes that the firm's resources in the telecommunication sector in Kenya, including all the assets, organizational processes, and capabilities, help in the easy implementation of organizational strategies to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of organizational operations. Therefore, there is a need for telecommunication sector companies to have a maximum investment in modern technology for extensive organizational success.

A strategic resource is an organizational resource that significantly affect performance of an organization and should be highly valuable (Hoq & Chauhan, 2016). According to Benedetto and Mu (2018), practical strategic resource meets all the specific criteria that are highly valuable to minimize operational costs or increase customer value. Besides, the strategic management should be rare enough for the competitors not to use a similar resource to go ahead in the competition in terms of value and should be difficult to imitate or substitute to keep off the competitors from gaining parity. Additionally, Benedetto and Mu (2018) highlight that those organizations having adequate and primary strategic resources should be in the competitive lead over those competitors who lack such resources. Resources are gathered in the organization. Various organizations frequently use various resources to achieve their objectives.

Human resources form part of the strategic organizational resources and are significant in setting up policies and practicing the essentials. Following increased changes in the trends across the globe, there are challenges experienced when managing human resources, which are needed to be handled effectively for managing a diverse workforce (Mathis & Jackson, 2018). Marvel (2019) observed that human resource strategy is highly related to an organization's type, objectives and mission, and vision. Therefore, organizations may require several types of human resources for better performance measurement.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Performance of Kenyan County governments is crucial for both micro and macro-economic development. The national governments have encountered strategy implementation challenges just like any other organization. The concept of

devolution being new to the county governments has highly affected strategies for implementing the county projects (Hantiro & Maina, 2020). However much the county government of Garissa has put much effort in strategic planning and development in the past years, the county recorded a poor implementation of the county government strategic plans.

The inability to effectively implement the strategic plans by the implementers has been a critical contributor to the poor performance of the county government of Garissa. In 2020, the county government of Garissa was ranked 5th last out of the 47 counties in Kenya in terms of performance (Africa Governance and Research Foundation, 2020). Some of the common challenges experienced in the County Government of Garissa include embezzlement of funds, poor service delivery, increased corruption levels, and service delays.

In 2014, the National Government in collaboration with the County Government initiated a process to assess the capacity of national and county staff and rationalize the public service. The exercise dubbed Capacity Assessment and Rationalization of Public Service (CARPS) had to provide well-organized structures for the National and County Governments based on the functions allocated to each level of government, determine the existing resource gaps, and give recommendation on the modalities for undertaking the rationalization process in accordance with the relevant conventions, statutes, and laws. This exercise found huge gaps in terms of resources and management. Similarly, since the inception of County government, the counties have been experiencing a number of challenges in the performance management including inadequate funds, leadership wrangles, pending bills, inadequate human resource capacity and poor systems and structures among others, which continue to hamper service delivery (Dominic, 2020). Accordingly, in spite of the various measures being undertaken to ensure the units of devolution work to achieve their objectives, there are few studies on the performance management on counties as this is a new phenomenon in Kenya on organizational performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Pfeffer and Slancik formulated the Resource Dependent Theory in 1978. The theory emphasizes that an organization needs funding to sustain itself over the long run. The organizations can only obtain certain services from their unique context, and other organizations in this setting desire the same help. The theory looks at how external resources like raw materials that a company consumes influence organizational behavior. The notion is based on the ideas that controlling and gaining access to resources is a power basis and that resources are crucial for company success. Organizations frequently manage resources, thus policies must be carefully addressed to maintain unrestricted access to resources. The degree to which businesses are dependent on the environment and other organizations increases as they change how they obtain finance (Fink et al. 2006). Analyzing the studies on this theory reveals that the social change ideology (Emerson, 1962; Blau, 1964; Pfeffer, & Salancik, 1978) and ideas linked to control were used (Pfeffer: 2005, Wenner, 2008).

According to resource dependence theory, an actor's level of control over other people's resources is referred to as their level of power (Harris & Holden 2001). According to that concept, the resource-based relationship's rising disproportionate power puts pressure on the resource-dependent organization and brings with it the demand-acceptance need. In this regard, resource supply instability is among the most significant environmental problems that companies must deal with. The three components that make up the spectrum of resource dependency are resource accumulation, resource availability instability, and resource connectivity (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003; Fink et al, 2006).

Resource interconnectedness is defined by Pfeffer and Slancik (2003) as the quantity and nature of relationships or interactions between organizations, while resource dependence is defined as the features of power and authority that are frequently present in an organization's environment. Resource dependence theory, as it was noted in the context of this study, can assist in determining the extent of changes in resource availability, resource features, and resource allocation ambiguity, which are the key drivers of successful organizational management.

Empirical Literature Review

Amin, Ismail, Rasid, and Selemani (2014) conducted a study assessing the causes of human resources on public universities' performance. The study population consisted of 300 employees working in public universities. The respondents included management of the public universities, lecturers, and support staff. The research instrument consisted of 46 items that covered those practices of human resource management towards the performance of the public universities. It was determined by the study that several HR practices like training, recruitment, career planning, appraisal of performance,

employee participation, clear job definition, as well as effective employee compensation have a substantial association with success of public universities.

A survey by Altarawneh (2016) examined the impacts of strategic human resources on the performance of organizations in Saudi Arabia. The study made use of descriptive and longitudinal study designs. The research tool used in the study was self-administrated standardized questionnaires distributed to managers. The data collected were further analyzed with the help of multiple regression. Findings highlighted that human resource practices such as employee rewards, employee training, compensations, and preliminary tests affect commercial banks' performance in Saudi Arabia. The study further determined that human resource activities are highly significant in determining the performance of multiple organizations. In essence, conducting employee training helps in improving current employee performance and makes them highly qualified in enduring new workloads.

Kiai, Lewa, and Karimi (2019) study examined the influence of human resources' strategic management on the successful achievement of those firms listed on the NSE. The target population for the study included first level managers, inclusive of the head of the HR department and directors of firms in the selected firms. The total sample for the study included 136, who further responded to the study. Structured research questionnaires were used in achieving data collection. Linear correlation was used to carry out data analysis. The study determined a significant association linking strategic HR practices and the success of those firms listed in the Nairobi Security Exchange.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design employed by the research study was descriptive design. This design is recommended as it helped in the provision of accurate information. The target population of the study was Garissa County Government. The respondents on the other hand were made up of senior management officials within the county of Garissa. The sampling design for the study was stratified sampling method that enabled the target population be grouped in form of strata for equitable representation. The study sample size was 101 respondents. The data collection instrument for the study was semi-structured questionnaires that was useful in obtaining primary data. 10% of the study sample size was part of the pilot group from which they were not included in the final research. Content validity was used in testing the validity of the questions within the questionnaire whereas reliability was obtained following a test on Cronbach Alpha. Quantitative data achieved by the survey was presented in the form of mean averages. Besides, statistical analysis software version 25 was also incorporated into the data analysis. Analysis of the qualitative data was done through content analysis.

4. FINDINGS

The descriptive results of human resources are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Human Resources

Content	Mean	Std. Deviation	Coefficient of Variation (%)
Employees are motivated to enhance their performance-by-performance management systems developed by human resources.	1.61	0.38	23
Within the County, strategic human resources serve to build a sense of community and friendship.	1.59	0.31	19
Human resources are an important part of the County's overall strategic strategy, as they enable the county analyze its current HR policies and improve the workplace environment and employee relations.	1.76	0.26	15
Human resources can assist in settling workplace disputes.	1.94	0.38	20
Working towards achieving similar goals within the county government of Garissa encourages a greater team spirit.	1.63	0.29	18
Conducive working environment within the county government of Garissa enhances team spirit which further contributes towards improved performance	1.91	0.27	14
Aggegrate Index	1.74	0.32	18

The findings in table 4.6 above shows that employees are motivated to enhance their performance-by-performance management systems developed by human resources as determined by a significant mean value of 1.61 together with a standard deviation of 0.38, hence a high level of significance. As compared to other statements, there was more variation to the mean as indicated by a coefficient variation of 23%. The findings also determined that majority of the respondents agreed with the statement that within the County, strategic human resources serve to build a sense of community and friendship as indicated by mean value of 1.59 and a standard deviation of 0.31, hence high level of significance.

Generally, the respondents highlighted that human resources are an important part of the County's overall strategic strategy, as they enable the county analyze its current HR policies and improve the workplace environment and employee relations. This was determined by a significant mean value of 1.76, a standard deviation of 0.26 and coefficient variation of 15%. This shows that this statement has relatively less variation in relation to its mean value. Besides, majority of the respondents agreed with the statement that human resources can assist in settling workplace disputes, thereby influencing improved performance levels as determined by a significant mean value of 1.94 and a standard deviation of 0.38.

The study further determined that working towards achieving similar goals within the county government of Garissa encourages a greater team spirit among the human resource. This was indicated by a mean value of 1.63 and a coefficient of variation of 18% and is therefore significant as it has less variation relative to the mean. It was also determined from the study that conducive working environment within the county government of Garissa enhances team spirit which further contributes towards improved performance. This was indicated by a mean value of 1.91, standard deviation of 0.27 and coefficient variation of 14%. This shows that this statement has relatively less variation in relation to its mean value as compared to other statements

Results of Regression Analysis

Table 2: Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R Value	R Square	R Square Adjusted	Estimate Error
1	0.632 ^a	0.341	0.276	0.52629

From the findings, it was determined that human resources and organizational performance which were study dependent and independent variables had a positive and strong relationship. This was determined by an overall coefficient of correlation (R) to be 0.632 as indicated in the above table. It was also depicted from the analysis findings that 34.1% (R²=0.341). The findings translate that 34.1% of the performed projects in Garissa County can be explained by human resources.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE						
Model 1	Sum of squares	Df	Value	Average Square	F	Sig.
Regression	15.51	1		15.51	18.82	0.000 ^b
Residual	34.78	60		0.824		
Total	50.29	61				

There was a high significance level which has been justified by a p value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 which is useful in measuring significance level. From the presented findings in the above ANOVA table, the overall significance of the model was determined to be 0.000. This was highly significance as it was determined to be 0.05. A variation analysis was provided by the model. The squares' total sum and their residual sum were calculated to be respectively 15.51 and 34.78. A study of variance's findings have an indication of a mean value of 0.38. The regression of mean squares was determined to be 5.74. The findings from the model shows a substantial level of statistical significance. The findings from the model gives an illustration that all the study independent variables are indicators of the study dependent variable. This is demonstrated by a substantial F-statistical value of 14.37 with a p-value of 0.000b, which is less than 0.05 and so indicates a high level of significance.

Table 4: Coefficients

Coefficients					
Model: Constant	Un-standardized coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B Value	Error Std.	β	T	Sig.
Constant	1.31	0.445		2.947	0.004
Human Resources	0.44	.167	0.354	2.370	0.008

The findings as determined from the above table highlights the beta results for establishing the statistical model as illustrated below;

Performance of Garissa County Government = 1.310 + 0.440 Human Resources

The researcher was keen to determine the influence of strategic resources on the performance of the County Government of Garissa, Kenya with the use of regression analysis. From the findings, it is evident from the model that when all the factors are constant, the performance of Garissa County Government stood at 1.310. On the other hand, with $\beta_1 = 0.440$, $t = 2.370$, $p = 0.008$ and $\alpha = 0.05$. The β_1 which was positive indicates that human resources have a positive and direct influence on the performance of Garissa County Government. Therefore, having an addition of just a unit of human resources increases performance of Garissa County by 0.440 in a similar direction.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Concerning the findings from the study, succeeding conclusions were made. It was concluded from the study findings that human resources greatly affect the County government of Garissa's performance. With the positive correlation between human resources and the performance of Garissa County, it was also concluded that human resources are an important part of the County's overall strategic strategy. This is because they enable the County to analyze its current HR policies and improve the workplace environment and employee relations. Besides, a conducive working environment within the county government of Garissa enhances team spirit, further contributing to improved performance.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that the county directors need to ensure the right employees who can work towards achieving similar goals within the county government of Garissa to encourage a greater team spirit are hired. Besides, the county government directors in Garissa County need to create an enabling environment to achieve increased performance through employee motivation.

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